

ONLINE BANKING AS THE NEW ERA OF BANKING

Dr. Binita Nanda*

*Ph.D. in Commerce, Ravenshaw University, Cuttack
Faculty in Commerce, J.K.B.K Govt. College, Cuttack, Odisha.

Email ID- binita.nanda18@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

With the coming up of online banking, electronic funds transfer and other similar products & services for funds transfer within quick time which was impossible a few years ago. The transfer from the traditional banking to e-banking has been an elevating improvement in banking dealings. Reserve Bank in its vision statement has set the objective to proactively promote electronic payments with an objective towards cashless society. This paper aims at analyzing the electronic transaction system adopted in Online Banking and their uses in the last five year. Further, it also studies the most important challenges faced by the banking industries by adopting online banking and the future prospects of online banking that can help in the growth of banking sector in India.

KEYWORDS- Bank, Online, Online transfer, E-banking, E-payment, NEFT, RTGS, UPI

INTRODUCTION

Globalization has exhaustively transformed the face of Indian banking industry from last few years. Banks have usually been in the front position of exploiting technology to improve their products/services and working competence. Over a long period of time banks have been utilizing electronic and telecommunication modes for distributing a wide range of valuable integrated services. The transaction channels include the public network, private networks etc. and the devices include smart phones, computers, Automated Teller Machines etc. The extensive utilization of computers, laptops, tablet, mobile phones etc. make too easy access to internet and World Wide Web. This form of banking is actually referred to as electronic form of banking or E Banking, while the range of services offered by different banks differ considerably both in their content and style. From the perspective of banks, banking services is being offered through internet, plastic cards, ATMs, smart phones, e-banking is nothing more than traditional banking services distributed through an electronic communication system. There are not many inventions that have transformed the business of banking as expeditiously as the e-banking revolution. Entire World over the banks is reutilizing their business strategies towards new opportunities to be offered by e-banking. E- Banking has enabled banks to extent borders and thus brings up new opportunities.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

1. To study various recent trends of e-banking, in particular- Electronic Transactions and Unified Payment Interface.
2. To analyze few challenges and future prospects in e-banking faced in an organisation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This part involves some specific techniques that are adopted in the research process to collect and evaluate data. This paper is a conceptual and analytical work using various secondary data such as published sources of data collected from various research papers and data from RBI website.

RECENT TRENDS

1. Electronic Transactions

It is electronic fund transfer or exchange of money from one account to another account which can take place across multiple financial institutions

National Electronic fund Transfer (NEFT) – This system facilitates individuals, firms and corporate one-to-one funds transfer from any bank branch to any individual, firm or corporate having an account with any other branch of a bank in the country having the NEFT system.

Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS) – With this system, the transfer of funds takes place from one bank to another bank on the basis of:

- a) a real time settlement, that means payment transaction is not supposed to any waiting period or delayed and,
- b) on gross basis of settlement, that means transaction is settled on one to one basis. This is one of the fastest ways of fund transfer system through the banking channel system.

The table below shows a comparative analysis of RTGS and NEFT transactions (In millions Rupees) for the last five years. It clearly represents that the amount of transfer of funds through NEFT is comparatively much more than that of RTGS in all these five years. Also, it reveals that the use of NEFT has increased widely in comparison with the RTGS system, as in RTGS the number of transactions stands at 136.6 millions, whereas the number of transactions via NEFT has substantially increased from 927.6 million in financial year 2014-15 to 2318.9 millions in financial year 2018-19.

Table representing number of transactions via RTGS and NEFT system in India

Year	No. of transactions (in Millions)	
	RTGS	NEFT
2014-15	92.8	927.6
2015-16	98.3	1252.9
2016-17	107.8	1622.1
2017-18	124.4	1946.4
2018-19	136.6	2318.9

2. Unified Payments Interface:

Unified Payments Interface (UPI) is a payment system which allows its users to link more than one bank account in a single smart phone app and can transfer fund without being having to provide IFSC code or account number.

The table below shows number of transactions using UPI system in India. The extensive use of UPI is clearly seen in the last five years where the number of transactions has increased from around Ten millions in financial year 2014-15 to 5353 millions in financial year 2018-19. With the advancement of various UPI systems such as Google Pay, Phone Pe, PayTM etc, it is revealed that the transactions via UPI is comparatively more than those of RTGS and NEFT.

Table representing number of transactions (in millions) using UPI in India

Year	No. of transactions (in Millions)
2014-15	10.1
2015-16	12.5
2016-17	17.9
2017-18	915.2
2018-19	5353.4

TWO MOST IMPORTANT CHALLENGES FACED BY E-BANKING

- **Customer Awareness:** Awareness among consumers about the e-banking facilities and procedures is still at a lower side in Indian scenario. Banks are not being able to circulate proper information about the use, benefits associated with internet banking system. Less awareness of new technologies and their benefits is among one of the major barrier in the development of e-banking.
- **Privacy Risk:** On account average computer literacy in India, many consumers are influenced by the risk of disclosing private information and fear of identity theft. This act as a barrier to the accessibility of e-banking services provided.

FUTURE PROSPECTS OF E-BANKING

- **Increasing Internet Users & Computer Literacy:** Today internet user and computer awareness is increasing at an alarming rate which has provided the biggest opportunity for E-Banking system. Banking industry still needs to en-cash this opportunity to attract more internet users to adopt internet banking.

- **Internet Banking:** It's clear that online finance will pickup and there will be increasing convergence in terms of product offerings banking services, share trading, insurance, loans, based on the data warehousing and data mining technologies. Anytime anywhere banking will become common with time, which could include banks to launch separate internet banking services other than traditional banking services.

CONCLUSION

E-Banking is a non-reversible phenomenon which will be gaining more amount of momentum in the coming years. With digitalization of Indian economy and move to turn India into cashless society, e-banking is going to be strengthened. In Indian banking scenario E-Banking has paved way to the exemplar shift from the seller's market to buyer's market. This shift has changed the approach of banks from conventional banking to convenience banking and from mass banking to class banking. The shift has increased the accessibility of banking facilities to a larger number of common people. In years to come E-Banking will not only be acceptable mode of banking but will be the most preferred mode of banking in India.

REFERENCES

- <http://www.rbi.org.in>
- Mohan, K. (2006), 'Information Technology on Indian banking', SCMS Journal of Indian Management, July-Sept issue, pp. 18-24.
- Shukla, R. and Shukla, P. (2011). 'E-banking: Problems and Prospects', International Journal of Management & Business Studies, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp.23-25.
- Reserve Bank of India (2014-15) to (2018-19) , Annual Report